

Quantum Probability and Coordinate Systems Part II

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In classical physics, physical trajectories of particles are tracked in time and space. In quantum mechanics, one creates conditional probabilities (wavefunctions) which often do not contain time such as in bound states or time-independent scattering. These may be influenced by physical trajectories, but as probability functions containing no time, they may be rewritten as a series of basis functions which have no link to the trajectory symmetry. For example, $\exp(ikz)$ is a wavefunction of an incoming beam of particles and expresses the physical symmetry of motion along the z axis with momentum k. It, however, may be written in spherical coordinates which contain conditional probability functions $\exp(ikr)/r$ and $\exp(-ikr)/r$ which have nothing to do with the physical trajectory symmetry. Scattered particles, however, move in radial lines so $\exp(ikr)/r$ describes scattered motion. One must be able to distinguish mathematically between conditional probabilities involved with different physical behaviour i.e. $\exp(ikr)/r$ from $\exp(ikz)$ versus from a scattered particle. This leads to the idea of the history of interactions being incorporated in the conditional probability in the form of a phase shift as statistics deals with “free particles” so the form $\exp(iS)$ should still hold, even if interactions occur. The “history” arises in the wavefunction if one considers an “and” probability situation which takes into account interactions. Thus, a wave function is a product of many probabilities, each representing a little region Δx (in one dimension for example). The purpose of this note is to examine these ideas in more detail.

Classical Trajectory

A main idea of classical physics is that one may follow the trajectory of a particle i.e. track $(x, t, dx/dt, d^2x/dt^2, \dots)$. Thus, one follows the history of the particle in time, but for a given x and t , is not really interested in the particle history. All that matters is its velocity (acceleration) at x and t . This carries over into classical statistical mechanics where one is interested in two body collisions at specific x points (even though time is removed in such a case).

In quantum time-independent scenarios, one writes a relative conditional probability i.e. the wavefunction which holds over space. As a statistical theory, it describes “free particles”, but the probability may not be written as a real, positive constant as in the classical situation. The closest scenario seems to be to describe a free particle as $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. a periodic function with modulus 1 for all x . A classical trajectory is incorporated in this scenario as $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with one direction motion with momentum p along the x axis. According to probability theory, “or” probabilities add and this may also be applied to the relative conditional probability i.e. the wavefunction. This, however, allows one to create “or” scenarios describing one kind of classical trajectory (i.e. radial motion) which add to create a classical trajectory with a completely different symmetry i.e. motion in the z direction or $\exp(ikz)$. In other words (1):

$$\exp(ikz) = \sum_l (2l+1) P_l(\cos(\alpha)) [\exp(ikr)/r + \exp(-ikr)/r] \quad r \rightarrow \infty \quad ((1))$$

This has been described in (2). In this note, we wish to describe consequences of such a feature, namely that $\exp(ikr)/r$ (for example) may be used to describe a radially scattered particle (i.e. mimic its classical trajectory) and at the same time be used to rewrite $\exp(ikx)$. This leads to the question: How does one distinguish between the two?

Tracking History in Quantum Mechanics

Given that quantum mechanical wavefunctions do not need to always be described in terms of a classical trajectory (e.g. $\exp(ikz)$ may be described as spherical probability waves), it seems that physical interactions which may occur need to be incorporated in a wavefunction, in other words "history". Given that one insists on describing "free particles", the form $\exp(iS)$ should be retained, suggesting that physical interactions (or distinguishing histories) may be described by a phase.

One example includes a radially scattered wave $\exp(ikr)/r$. The wave is scattered due to the interaction with a potential and this history must be incorporated to distinguish it from $\exp(ikr)/r$ used to "build" $\exp(ikz)$. Thus, one writes $\exp(i(kr + \text{phaseshift}))/r$ for the radially scattered wave. A second example is that of two identical particles with one traveling further than the other to reach a potential region (e.g. slits). The first arrives at x as $\exp(ikx)$ and the second travels further and arrives as $\exp(ikx + \text{phase})$. One cannot physically distinguish and does no measurement to do so and the two interfere with the extra phase being important.

Thus, time-independent quantum mechanics seems to be a probabilistic theory which considers the physical history of a particle including extra interactions with potentials (as in scattering or the Bohm-Aharonov effect) or extra distances travelled. Including the history in the form of a phase shift is a way to distinguish between physical scenarios as the probability basis functions may be used for many scenarios i.e. spherical $\exp(ikr)/r$ may be used to describe $\exp(ikz)$. It seems, however, that more is involved.

Product Probabilities

In the previous section, we discussed the idea of the history of a trajectory being incorporated in a phase i.e. the history of interactions. For models which consider physical cycling i.e. a physical classical wave or zitterbewegung, an interaction may disrupt the physical cycling, thus leading to a physical difference in a particle which has interacted and one which has not. In this note, we do not wish to consider physical cycling. Instead, we argue that the "history" or phase shift may be due to a product of relative conditional probabilities. In other words, $\exp(ikx) = \exp[i(k\delta(x_1) + k\delta(x_2) + k\delta(x_3) + \dots)] = \text{Product over } i \exp(i k \delta(x_i))$. Thus, the probability at a given x is due to an "and" situation of many tiny $\delta(x)$ steps.

Consider a particle with momentum k entering a Bohm-Aharonov region with a magnetic potential A , but no magnetic B field. The fact that B is zero may be an average effect. It is possible there are still virtual photon hits from A , they just do not accelerate i.e. change k , the momentum on average. The momentum, however, may fluctuate due to virtual photon kicks as the particle travels through the region with $A(x)$. Thus in such a region, one does not have $\exp(ik\delta(x_1)) \exp(i\delta(x_2)) \dots$. Rather, one may have: $Z_1 = \exp(i k_1 \delta(x_2)) \exp(i k_2 \delta(x_2))$

...Upon exiting the region, one again has: $Z_2 = \exp(i k \Delta(x_n)) \exp(i k \Delta(x_{n+1}))$ etc. Z_1 may be rewritten as $\exp(i k \Delta X + i \text{phaseshift})$ where X is the length of the region in which $A(x)$ acts. Thus, the phase shift is really a consequence of changing momentum (possibly stochastically) within a small region and one considers an “and” situation which automatically incorporates the “history” of the trajectory. Thus, a particle with k which encounters no potential A will have a different product probability than one which does. Given that both have the same k , they are indistinguishable and so there is interference.

Indistinguishability

Even though one may have two different physical trajectories in a system i.e. an incoming beam moving along the z axis and radially scattered particles and one may use spherical $\exp(ikr)/r$ to describe both (with a phase added to the scattered particle), the incoming and scattered particles are still indistinguishable. Thus, one must still add wavefunctions for the two trajectories. Thus, one still writes:

$$\exp(ikz) + f(\theta, \phi) [\exp(ikr + i \text{phaseshift})/r] \quad ((2))$$

As a result, there is interference ((2)), but the history of interaction (in the form of the phaseshift) for the scattered particle is part of this interference.

Quantum Bound States

The above ideas may be applied to a quantum bound state, even though this may not involve coordinate changes. Consider a stochastic potential ($V(x)$ on average) which knocks a particle into different momentum states. At x , one expects a momentum distribution with:

$$P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x) \text{ where } W(x) = \sum \text{over } p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

One uses free particle relative conditional probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ because statistics deals with free particles.

According to the above section, one should “add” wavefunctions for different physical scenarios incorporating an appropriate phase to describe the history of each. A particle that is knocked into a state with momentum p has a phase of px so one has $\exp(ipx)$. A different momentum p_1 has a phase p_1x so $\exp(ip_1x)$ etc. It seems that the same idea is at work in the momentum distribution of a bound state. One does not need to add an extra phase shift because ipx is the phase shift and one has only one particle, so it is indistinguishable with itself. Because the particle is continually receiving stochastic hits, the history only applies to the point x i.e. to the time the particle had p at x , then at another time p_1 at x etc. One cannot trace the history beyond this in the equilibrium situation i.e. bound state situation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, quantum mechanics, unlike classical mechanics, does not have to be described in terms of a physical trajectory, although it is usually influenced by it. For example, particles moving along the z axis which then scatter spherically off a potential have two symmetries (or kinds of trajectories). The first is linear in the z direction and the second along radial lines. Given that quantum mechanics describes a conditional probability function of the form $\exp(ikz)$ (so that that modulus is 1, then a particle moving along a radial line should have a conditional probability of $\exp(ikr)/r$ (with r related to $rrdr$ d solid angle). In other words, $\exp(ikz)$ may be written mathematically in terms of $\exp(ikr)/r$ and one may have one symmetry in the problem. One must, however, distinguish between $\exp(ikr)/r$ from $\exp(ikz)$ and $\exp(ikr)/r$ from a scattered particle. This occurs through the idea of product “and” probabilities which automatically track this history. A particle that is scattered in a radial direction has undergone a physical reaction. Even though this reaction may be elastic, while the interaction occurred, the momentum may have been changing. This process may be described by adding a phase to $\exp(ikr)/r$ i.e. $\exp(i(kr+\text{phaseshift}))/r$.

This same idea is more clearly seen by considering a particle moving through a region with a magnetic potential $A(x)$ and no magnetic field B . On average there is no force, but there may be virtual photon hits changing momentum within the region of $A(x)$. Thus, a product wavefunction is no longer $\exp(i k \Delta x_1) \exp(i k \Delta x_2) \dots$, but rather $\exp(i k_1 \Delta x_1) \exp(i k_2 \Delta x_2) \dots \exp(i k \Delta x_n)$. The first set of products may be rewritten as $\exp(i k X) \exp(i \text{phaseshift})$ where X is the region within which $A(x)$ acts. Thus, phaseshifts describing history arise from product or “and” conditional probabilities and lead to interference between indistinguishable particles which have undergone different interaction schemes (which have not altered their momentum).

Finally, a bound quantum state may be described by a momentum distribution at each x with the conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$. Here, one has an “or” situation with all different possible phases i.e. different ipx . The idea of phase shift representing hits by the stochastic potential (which is $V(x)$ on average) is again present. In this case, the potential creates the different phases ipx and as there is only one particle (indistinguishable with itself), one adds the wavefunctions ($\exp(ipx)$) with each phase or “interaction history at x ”.

References

1. Shankar, R. Principles of Quantum Mechanics (Plenum, 1980)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Probability and Coordinate Systems(preprint, zenodo, 2020)